

Early Appearance And Distribution Of Lipofuscin Pigment In Brain Cells Of Rattus Rattus

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Abstract In the present investigation, the histochemical nature and early observation of lipofuscin pigment in brain cells, paraffin section were cut at 6µ and stained with Nile blue A, ferric ferricyanide, the stained sections were examined under light microscope. In pre mature age level pigment accumulation in brain cells of *Rattus Rattus* Nile blue A reacted moderately and mildly affinities with Carbol fuchsin.

Keywords Lipofuscin, Histochemical Nature, Rattus Rattus **Brain, Nile blue A, Carbol fuchsin.

Introduction Aging is considered a natural physiological process through which an organism gradually grows older. It is characterized by a progressive decline or loss of adaptability with advancing age. Aging can also be defined as a permanent arrest of cell division associated with characteristic phenotypic changes. This phenomenon was first described by Leonard Hayflick in human fibroblasts that were serially passaged in culture (Hayflick and Moorhead, 1961).

Objective of study The objective of this paper is to study the early appearance and distribution of lipofuscin pigment in brain cells of Rattus Rattus

Review of Literature Lipofuscin is the product of the cell metabolism in post mitotic cells as secondary lysosomes when lipofuscin pigments are activated with blue and ultraviolet light, lipofuscin pigments are emitted yellow to green flurosecent fletcher *et al* 1973 .qualitative and histochemical stainy method used by Sheehy in neurons. Fletcher *et al* 1973 and study of histological, histochemical and quantitative method used by Sheehy in neurons. Histochemical nature of lipofuscin stained by diverse staining process, pigment easily stained with methyl green, PAS reaction and ferric ferricyanide Marani and Lazarow 2017.

Methodology The material used in this study brain cells from premature age group. Tissues samples at age group of premature. Brain tissues were fixed in bouin's fluid and paraffin section cut at 6 u thickness. Histochemical studies were made in sections stained with Nile blue A and ferric ferricyanide.

Result and Discussion Results indicated that the lipofuscin pigment were not detected at first to three months with any stains histochemical nature in five months showed characteristically different staining behaviour due to differences in the composition of liocofuscin pigment. It was clearly noted that licofuscin granules in brain cells of five months were easily stained with nile blue A and carbolfuchsin ferric ferricyanide and carbolfuchsin stains does showing a mildly positive nile blue A, however reacted moderately positive with ferric ferricyanide and carbolfuchsin stains.

Histochemical nature of licofuscin in brain cells at the six month showed moderately positive with nile blue A and ferric ferricyanide, however strongly positive with carbolfuchsin stains.

Lipofuscin pigment in heart of dysdercus similarly these stains used in gupta *et al*.

Characteristics Of Lipofuscin Pigment Granules In Brain Cells Of First Age Group

Age Group	Tissues	Morphological characteristics of lipofuscin pigment	Distribution of lipofuscin pigment

1	Brain	Heterogeneous and irregular	and	Irregularly scattered throughout the cytoplasm
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Histochemical Nature Of Lipofuscin Pigment In Different Tissues In First Age Group.

Age Group

Age Group	Tissues	Nile Blue A	Ferric Ferricyanide	Carbolfuchsin
		+	++	+++

+++Stongly positive, ++moderately positive, +mildly positive

Conclusion

First Observation Of The Lipofuscin Pigment Of Brain Cells Of Pre- Mature Age Carbol Fuchsin Stains*300.

References

1. Agarwal V. (1995), *histological & histochemical studies of certain organs in different age groups of Channa punctatus with special reference to lipofuscin with special reference to lipofuscin pigment. New report.*
2. Hayflick L, Moorhead PS. *The serial cultivation of human diploid cell stains. Exp Cell Res.*1961;25:585-621.[13905658]
3. Hyden, H. and Lindstrom, B. 1950; *Microspectrographic studies on the yellow pigment in nerve cells. Discussions. Faraday. Soc.* 9; 436-441.
4. FEW, A. AND GETTY, R. (1967).*Occurrence of lipofuscin as related to aging in the Canine and Porcine nervous system. J. Geront.* 22; 357-368.
5. GUPTA, R.C.SUNITA AND GUPTA D.P.(1989).*Histochemical studies on lipofuscinin heart, midgut and Malpighian tubule of male Dysdercus similis U.P.J.ZOOL.*9 (2)244-248
6. Nanda, B.S., and GETTY, R. (1971); *Lipofuscin pigment in the nervous system of aging pig. Exp. Geront* 6; 447-452.
7. SHARMA S.P. (1967).*Histochemical studies on the lipofuscins of certain cold blooded vertebrates Res.Bull.* 18; 213-219.
8. Sheehy, M.R.J (1990) *widespread occurrence of fluorescent morphological lipofuscin in the crustacean brain, J. Crust. Biol.* 10, 613-622.
9. Gupta, R.C. and Gupta, S. D.P. (1989). *Quantitative studies of lipofuscin in heart of Dysdercus similis. Geobios.* 16;208-210.